

HOLOBALANCE: An Augmented Reality virtual trainer solution for balance training and fall prevention

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Abstract— Balance disorders affect a large number of older people, leading to falls. To promote independence, self-care and the quality of living of the long-lived population, we are developing a solution to act as a virtual trainer for people that suffer from vestibular dysfunction related balance disorders. Our solution offers a virtual balance therapy, supported by Information and Communication Technology devices, to monitor user's activity during the day and provide real time feedback for the correct execution of physiotherapy exercises. Wearable sensors are utilized to monitor user activity, while during the execution of exercises, cameras are used to track the body of the user. An Augmented Reality headset is used to project the virtual trainer's 3D avatar in front of the user, providing real time guidance for the correct execution of the exercises.

I. INTRODUCTION

A balance disorder is a condition that makes an individual feel unsteady or dizzy. It is estimated that more than 4 out of 10 Americans, sometime in their lifetime, will experience an episode of dizziness severe enough to ask for medical assistance [1]. Balance disorders can be provoked by certain health conditions, medication, or a problem in the inner ear or the brain. A balance disorder, such as the vestibular dysfunction characterized by vertigo, can widely impact daily activities and cause psychological and emotional hardship, and is a leading cause of death among the elderly [2], [3]. Balance control is enhanced when performing moderate and/or vigorous physical activity, resulting to fall prevention, especially on adults aged 65 years and above [4]. To improve balance control, exergames have been used in some studies, to motivate the users to perform exercises at their home.

In our solution we are going one step further, developing a virtual coach that will monitor and provide real time feedback to the user via a hologram avatar, during the execution of the rehabilitation and muscle strengthening exercises. Additionally, we will monitor the physical activity of the user outside home and will continuously evaluate and adjust the personalized recommendations, using motivation strategies. With our solution, we aim to develop a new form of accessible user interaction, based on holograms and Augmented Reality (AR) games, with customizable avatars and environments. The hologram will be a surrogate physiotherapist with daily presence in a user's home and provide ongoing remote support, while monitoring and

assessing daily activity and correctness of balance exercise performance.

II. BALANCE DISORDERS

A. Balance disorders

Many types of balance disorders require balance training, prescribed by an occupational therapist or physiotherapist [5]. Exercise is a key intervention for improving physical functions and restraining physical dependence in older adults. It has been shown to improve the different aspects of postural control. A large amount of research has been focused on balance enhancement and fall prevention through exercise programs for the elderly [6]–[9]. Physiotherapy sessions and muscle strengthening exercises usually take place at rehabilitation centers, as it has been proved that tailored fall prevention exercises (to the needs of each individual) may reduce falls up to 54% [10], [11]. Moreover, targeted exercise interventions executed in the home environment of the patient, have demonstrated improvement in the balance and strength function of older adults, reducing the number of fallers and multiple fallers [12]. Recent research indicates that home-based exercise sessions have better adherence rates than group-based community sessions and are effective in improving functional performance and balance in functionally impaired older adults [13].

B. Balance training

Balance control exercises may be performed in daily basis, in conjunction with cognitive training, to maintain and improve functional and mental capacity of people over the age of 55 years, without the diagnosis of any pre-existing cognitive problems [14]. In recent years, body tracking sensors have been used, to identify and assess the posture of the user during the execution of muscle-strengthening workouts (in the form of exergames), offering complimentary rehabilitation sessions at home [15], [16]. Moreover, apart from the accomplishment of the exercises or the exergames, there is the need of a virtual trainer, to motivate the patient and promote the compliance to the exercise program. Past studies have used exergames and virtual trainers for physiotherapy and occupational therapy at home [17].

In our solution, we are developing a virtual coach, to promote the balance of older adults, through a series of personalized physiotherapy exercises. We are using an Augmented Reality (AR) headset to project a virtual trainer, in the form of a hologram, in the environment of the user, to provide real time feedback in the execution of physiotherapy exercises for balance improvement. The design of the system

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and the monitoring of the patients are supported by a group of healthcare professionals, specialized in rehabilitation and vestibular rehabilitation, incorporating optokinetic stimulation [18].

III. PERSONALIZED VIRTUAL COACHING

In contrast to the abovementioned positive outcomes of exercise for the elderly, training effects vanish when exercise sessions are missed. Home based training programs are more convenient for older adults, although a frequent problem is the poor adherence due to a lack of motivation [19]. To overcome this problem, a virtual coach that interacts with the user, would not require the physical presence of a person during the execution of the rehabilitation exercises. Virtual coaches have been mostly implemented as embodied conversational characters, that communicate with the user through natural language understanding and motion capture. Compared to self-administered training via written and audio material, virtual coaching better facilitates the establishment of a regular practice by the user, providing supervision and real-time feedback [20], [21].

In our solution, we aim to develop a virtual coaching platform that will support persons with balance disorders to improve compliance and adherence to their balance training schedule, while at the same time improve self-management and self-monitoring of their physical activity. Audio-visual, real time feedback has been proved to be highly beneficial for the patient, in absence of a physiotherapist, while performing balance training exercises, in the home environment, with the aid of a balance board [22]. To improve motivation and tailor the interventions for each individual, we will incorporate nonverbal behavior recognition and affective computing to better evaluate the user and adjust the training to his/her needs.

A. Virtual Reality

In other studies, Virtual Reality (VR) has been used to overcome any temporal and spatial limitations and has been employed for simulating complex, risky and costly tasks, such as sports activity, flight simulation, surgical techniques and rehabilitative tools for people with various diseases [23]. As supervision and feedback are essential elements for an effective training outcome, VR coaches have the ability to adapt to the knowledge and needs, as well as to the motivational and affective state of the trainee [24]. Several studies have shown that when older adults underwent a VR-based exercise program, they were highly motivated and their balance control was increased significantly [23].

Although VR headsets are usually used in relevant applications, a common problem is that those devices isolate the user from the surrounding objects and environment and may result to nausea or dizziness [25]. To overcome such drawbacks, we will develop the virtual coach using AR, embedding the coach in the home environment of the patient. The coach will be in the form of a three-dimensional avatar, presented as a hologram in the space in front of the user. This avatar will interact with the user during the

execution of the rehabilitation exercises and will give real time feedback on the correct execution of the exercises.

B. Augmented Reality

Using AR, the user does not interact with a computer-generated world but with the real world, including computer-generated objects. AR applications, especially when designed for educational purposes, sharpen user's investigation, processing and spatial skills, while concurrently increase motivation [26], [27]. AR games are able to improve the executive and cognitive functions and, in some cases, even the social relationships of a person [28]. They have been applied as ageing-in-place, entertainment, rehabilitation and training tools for the elderly [29], [30] and, if combined with machine learning classification and basic reasoning methods, they constitute cognitive tools that become affected by the user's action and the environment's state [31]. Three-dimensional holography, combined with AR technology, has been used to train older adults and, as a result, improved their mental rotation and observation skills, while maintaining their interest [32]. In our system, we are embedding a headset with near-eye displays, to sense the environment of the user and his/her movement as well as to place the avatar of the trainer in front of the patient. Scanning the environment and identifying the location of the walls, we are also projecting various environments around the patient, during the execution of the exercises, defined by the Expert Group, for the vestibular rehabilitation therapy. The set of the exercises that are performed with the use of the AR headset, are mainly habituation exercises, used to treat symptoms of dizziness produced because of the self-motion of the patient, or because of various visual stimuli. Such exercises are indicated for patients who report increased dizziness while moving around, especially when making sudden head movements.

IV. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

As the overall objective of our system is the development of a new personalized coaching platform, based on virtual reality and augmented reality tools, for motivation and support of the ageing population with balance disorders, we have defined the following components: (i) the monitoring and interaction module, (ii) the cloud hosted core platform, (iii) the AR based virtual coach and (iv) the expert panel.

A. Architecture outline

The overview of HOLOBALANCE system architecture is depicted in Figure 1. The Exergames Platform, along with the AR headset and the wearable sensors, are located in the home of the user, simulating the environment of the clinician's office (or rehabilitation center), where the balance control exercises would be executed. Data Processing module is the backbone of the platform. This module is hosted on a cloud infrastructure, making use of FIWARE protocol for data exchange [33], to promote interoperability of data processing on the cloud backbone of the system. The expert panel, doctors will monitor adherence and performance of exercise execution, via an intuitive and user-friendly web interface, and will be able to decide

alterations/modifications of the personalized training program. During the execution of the exercises, an AR headset (equipped with a gyroscope and a camera to measure head and eye movement) will be used to capture adherence to the exercise execution and provide vocal instructions during the procedure. Body posture and skeleton motion will be captured through a sensor that will use a mean-shift algorithm to perform 2D tracking in live RGB images. 3D tracking will then be performed through the use of the Iterative Closest Point algorithm. Finally, a smartphone application will be used for the communication between users and carers, the creation of users' profiles and the interaction of the virtual communities. Exercise data will be processed locally (due to the requirement to provide real time feedback to the user), whereas, all the other components of the system (Figure 1) will be hosted in a cloud infrastructure.

Figure 1 - Overview of system architecture

Emotional computing and behavioral modeling tools will aim to collect the emotional state of the users and develop mechanisms that can be personalized and predict future behavior. Big data analytics services and machine learning techniques will be combined to implement the concept of progressive learning, where new knowledge about the training performance of both a single patient or/and a sum of the patients will be continuously used to refine and modify the index of physiotherapy and cognitive training. All this information will be promoted to the virtual coach and the expert panel.

The main component of virtual coaching will be augmented reality hologram models that will be used for balance physiotherapy. These models will be combined with three-dimensional biomechanical models. Unity3D will be used for the creation of the holograms and their incorporation into the real environment. The physiotherapy will be reinforced by cognitive training and augmented reality game technologies that include dual tasking and thus switch attention between the cognitive and physical activities. Moreover, auditory training and speech recognition will be used through the AR glasses as part of the cognitive training. At the moment we are testing Microsoft HoloLens and Meta AR headsets in a focus group, to identify which one performs better and is more acceptable by the users. The main differences between the two devices are the field of view (HoloLens 35° vs. Meta 90°) and the fact that HoloLens are completely wireless.

All patients' state and training performance will be monitored by the experts of the system through visual analysis tools. The experts will be able to monitor the state of all patients, draw conclusions and make modifications on a training schedule, according to each individual's performance and needs.

B. Sensors and devices

In HOLOBALANCE project, pressure sensitive insoles, a smart band, body motion capture and AR glasses will be combined to provide a hologram based solution, as a virtual coach. The insoles will analyze standing balance and gait during walking, using an array of pressure-sensitive sensors and inertial measurement units [34]–[36]. A wrist mounted smart band or smartwatch, equipped with accelerometers, gyroscopes, optical sensors, microphones and contact sensors, will be used in our system to monitor physiological parameters (heart rate, heart rate variability etc.), Galvanic Skin Response and overall daily activity (i.e. number of steps, distance walked per day, sleep quality etc).

Using optical motion capture technology, a depth sensing camera will be used to track human motion in real-time [37]. The data from the motion capture sensor will be combined with the data collected from the AR headset and the pressure sensitive insoles, to accurately track the movement of the user (degrees of incline, speed of head movement and rotation - yaw, pitch and roll), to adjust the 3D hologram of the virtual coach that is projected during exercise execution and provide instructions to the user, through an audiovisual feedback. In that sense, the virtual coach will provide an ongoing daily activity coaching, regarding exercise performance, physical activity levels and compliance with exercise goals, to enhance the self-management of users.

C. Monitoring and feedback

The expert panel is the main tool for the experts of the system. Physiotherapists, Ear Nose Throat Experts, psychologists and cognitive training experts can be informed of the accuracy and properties of the exercises performed by the patients. They can monitor and also make modifications on the existing training program, consisting of balance physiotherapy exercises, cognitive training tasks and a physical activity plan, according to the performance, the needs and the personalized plan of each patient. These changes and interventions are transferred through the cloud infrastructure to the virtual coaching interaction tools.

The expert panel will define the appropriate User Interfaces for all the different types of users, taking into account the experts' requirements. Given the need to visualize large amounts of heterogeneous data that derive from many distinctive sources, novel visualization approaches will be applied. Specifically, a number of visual analytics services components will enable the simultaneous representation of multi-dimensional data at varying levels of abstraction and offer the opportunity to filter the group of patients and their features. Experts will be able to supervise the state of all patients as well as general information about specific

distributions (e.g. gender), in order to draw conclusions and subsequently share them with the rest of the experts and carers. Moreover, a new family of visually-driven anomaly detection algorithms will be applied to detect abnormalities in the input of the cross-domain data and give visual or textual explanations for the majority of them, in the form of status reports. Apart from the modifications on the exercise program, experts will also be able to make personalized diet recommendations and offer safety precautions, which will be shown to the patient through the hologram and the smart glasses during training.

V. FUTURE WORK

At the moment, we have started the comparison of the latest devices for the representation of the AR supported virtual trainer and during the following months, our medical and technical teams will perform demonstrations on selected adults (symptomatic and asymptomatic) to get an initial feedback on the system. The data collected by the focus groups will be used to better understand how our solution needs to be modified to offer the best user experience and be customized to the needs of the individuals with balance disorders.

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